

Influence of the Field Type (Mountain and Plain) on the Cupric Status of Lambs

Authors : Mouna Mallem, Majid Tlidjane

Abstract : The study realized on alive lambs in two different areas mountain and plain in Batna region, aims to demonstrate the possible effect of field type on cupric status of lambs, through evaluation of copper contents in the chain: soil-plant-animal by atomic absorption spectrophotometry. This comparative study also allowed the investigation of the influence of age and season. The results obtained show that contents of copper in the soil, forage in the same way as in the plasma of lambs are higher in the plain than in the mountainous area, and however the difference is significant only between the values of feed.

Keywords : copper, forage, lambs, plasma copper

Conference Title : ICAE 2014 : International Conference on Agricultural Engineering

Conference Location : Montreal, Canada

Conference Dates : May 12-13, 2014